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Revolutionary energy storage cycle with carbon free aluminium

Definition of the LCA Framework

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Forewords

This deliverable is the first of three for Life Cycle Assessment of the REVEAL project concept. The goal and scope definition are the first step of any LCA study (ISO 14040/44). It includes documentation of the goal and the scope of the study, including methodological choices. For instance, the system boundaries of the LCA study are set in order not to exclude relevant parts of the life cycle and to allow for a fair comparison between systems. End of life modelling and related allocation will be a focal point because the fate of disused smelter or converter components could be an important factor in the results. Relevant impact categories are selected, and a choice is made on the impact assessment method. Data requirements are being specified along with any assumptions, limitations and initial data quality requirements.

This is a second version of the document with improved focus on objective of the work.

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Terms, definitions, and abbreviated terms

Al	Aluminium
Alu-to-Energy	Aluminium to energy conversion process
CHP	Combined Heat and Power plant
CO	Carbon Oxide
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
FU	Functional unit
GA	Grant Agreement
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
NIC	NIC, Slovenia
NO _x	nitric oxide and nitrogen dioxide
OST	OST, Switzerland
Power-to-Alu	Power to aluminium process
Power-to-CH ₄	Power to methane energy storage system
Power-to-H ₂	Power to hydrogen energy storage system
Power-to-methanol	Power to methanol energy storage system
PRé	PRé Sustainability, the Netherlands
RF	Reference flow
VOC	Volatile organic compounds

Task 6.1 Definition of the LCA Framework

1.1 Introduction

The EU Horizon Europe project REVEAL – Revolutionary Energy Storage Cycle based on sustainable carbon free aluminium, is a project that aims to develop a new technical solution for the seasonal storage of large amounts of energy with an energy storage density of more than 15 MWh/m³ at low cost for the production of heat and electricity in winter. The project is highly multi-disciplinary, as it combines among others chemical engineering, mechanical engineering, thermodynamics, environmental, economic and social sciences which is covered by the wide variety of stakeholders within the consortium.

The REVEAL project involves nine partners from seven different European countries (Iceland, Germany, Slovenia, the Netherlands, Czech Republic, Switzerland and Norway). Among the partners there are research institutes and universities summing up to a total of four R&D partners (OST, IceTec, NIC and SINTEF) and five SMEs (Ratiotherm, PRé Sustainability, Arctus, EHgroup and Fenix). REVEAL brings an interdisciplinary consortium together, which is representative at the European level and covers all relevant aspects with strong scientific and technological background, strengthened by economic (Ratiotherm, Arctus) and environmental (PRé Sustainability) expertise.

The new technology aims to reduce the emission of greenhouse gasses of energy systems. Therefore, the LCA will give more insight into the environmental performance of the REVEAL storage system compared to conventional energy systems. The study will follow ISO 14040/44 as much as possible, except for the third-party critical review. [1], [2].

This deliverable presents the goal and scope of the study, including the geographical scope, data used, allocation procedures and impact assessment method used in the study. Ultimately, a full report will cover all four steps of the LCA, i.e.: Goal and scope definition; Life Cycle Inventory (LCI); Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA); and interpretation of the results, plus additional insights from the circularity of the proposed storage system (expressed with a so-called ‘material circularity indicator’).

LCA is an inherently iterative process Figure 1, meaning that insights gained throughout the different stages can be used to refine and improve earlier steps. Therefore, any findings that emerge from Tasks 6.2, Task 6.3, and Task 6.4 may be used to update and elaborate on the current goal and scope of the LCA. This approach ensures that the assessment remains aligned with the most accurate and relevant information as the project progresses

FIGURE 1 LCA FRAMEWORK

2. Goal and Scope

2.1 Goal of the study

There is a mismatch between renewable energy production in summer (solar, wind, hydro) and energy demand in winter (for heating) in many European countries. Therefore, there is a need to store renewable energy so that it can be used in winter when demand increases. The REVEAL storage system aims to solve this problem by storing renewable energy in carbon-free aluminium, which can be converted into heat and electricity during winter. Especially, heat is crucial during winter.

The new technology aims to reduce the environmental impact of energy use in winter; however, this has never been assessed. The goal of the study can be divided into four different reasons described below:

1. Gain insight into the environmental impact and circular economy performance of the REVEAL energy storage system throughout the entire life cycle.
2. Suggest improvement actions to improve sustainability, based on circularity indicators as well as environmental impact assessment – throughout the project and also for future research.
3. Compare the environmental impact of heating and providing electricity by an application using the power-to Alu storage cycle to conventional energy supply and other energy storage cycles (i.e., Power-to-X, hydrogen, methanol).
4. Explore alternative scenarios and use the findings in the product development process.

The report will be for internal and external use. Therefore, the communication will be twofold; on the one hand it is used to share the results of the REVEAL project publicly whereas the report will also be used internally to further improve the technology and reduce the environmental impact where possible.

The project will share its results specifically with the European Commission; however, the project also targets other stakeholders that might be interested in learning about/understanding and possibly using this technology in the future.

The project will also result in the development of a dataset of the REVEAL energy storage system, which can be used as an input in future LCA studies using this new technology. Therefore, this LCA study also targets stakeholders interested in using the developed LCI data.

2.2 System under study

The product under study is the REVEAL energy storage system and consists of two parts. The first part is the Power-to-Aluminium (Power-to-Alu) system, and the second part is the Aluminium-to-Energy (Alu-to-Energy) system (Fig. 1).

The Power-to-Alu process developed by IceTec and Arctus is a new technique to produce carbon free aluminium from renewable energy sources (mainly hydropower) in Iceland, which are in abundance. The aluminium is produced with a technique based on multiple vertical inert anodes and cathodes in low temperature electrolyte (800°C). In here, smelting occurs through electrolytic dissociation. The smelter produces aluminium from alumina (Al₂O₃) according to the following formula:

EQUATION 1 ALUMINIUM PRODUCTION FROM ALUMINA

In this process, one ton of oxygen is emitted for each ton of aluminium produced, and no fluorocarbons are formed. The inert electrode process being developed by Arctus and IceTec has the potential to be at least 20% more energy-efficient than the conventional Hall-Héroult process [3] and emits no greenhouse gases.

The aluminium is expected to be produced in Iceland, Norway or in other European countries where stable renewable energy is available. As a baseline, Iceland will be used in this study. Afterwards, the aluminium is shipped to Switzerland (baseline) or other countries with high energy demand during wintertime. Different countries will be assessed in the scenario analysis.

In Switzerland, the new Alu-to-Energy process is developed by OST, in which the aluminium is converted to H₂ and heat in an aqueous solution at low temperatures (<100 °C). The H₂ will thereafter be converted into electricity and heat in a fuel cell. The total output in heat and electricity can be used in a household. After the Alu-to-Energy converter, the aluminium is converted back into Al₂O₃ which is shipped back to the aluminium smelter in Iceland to use as raw material in the Power-to-Alu process.

Alternatively, a high temperature Alu-to-Energy process will be analysed in a scenario analysis in which Alu is reacting with water vapour at high temperatures (>200 °C) and is producing heat, hydrogen, and alumina (Al₂O₃). This route will produce energy with a higher exergetic yield, also suitable for industry.

The REVEAL energy storage system will be compared with three other energy storage systems:

1. The first energy storage system is the power-to-H₂ energy system. It is based on a process that converts electrical power to hydrogen (H₂) by using an electrolyzer to split water into hydrogen

- and oxygen, with an efficiency of 65-75%. The hydrogen can be stored either in cryogenic or pressurized form and used as an energy source later in time.
2. The second alternative is the power-to-CH₄/methanol technology. In here, electricity is again used to produce hydrogen, whereafter the hydrogen is converted into methane (CH₄) or methanol via chemical or biological methanation of carbon dioxide. The last step from hydrogen to methane adds another loss of ~25%, on top of the previously mentioned efficiency loss. Later in time, the methane/methanol is used to produce energy in which carbon is emitted.
 3. The third option is the combined heat and power (CHP) system using natural gas to produce energy in winter.

The REVEAL energy storage system aims at reducing the impact of stored energy compared to the conventional energy production like fossil fuels and other new storage systems. The main points of difference that are expected are:

- In comparison to Power-to-H₂: a higher volumetric energy density of 23.6 MWh/m³ at maximum (block of Al), and > 15 MWh/m³ in practice (Al grit used for the Alu-to-Energy units). Aluminium also has much safer handling and is easier to store and transport due to the extremely high flammability of hydrogen. These advantages are expected to lead to corresponding cost savings and environmental benefits.
- In comparison to Power-to-CH₄ and Power-to-methanol: no carbon source is needed, a two times higher volumetric energy density, and safer handling, potentially reducing the environmental impact.
- In comparison to a combined heat and power system using natural gas, no combustion with air for energy conversion and therefore no NO_x, VOC, CO and CO₂ emissions.

2.3 Functional unit and reference flow

The functional unit (FU) describes a quantification of the function or service provided by the product under study. It provides a reference to which the inputs and outputs of the product or system can be related. The amount(s) of the main product and possible auxiliary materials needed to fulfil the FU is/are called the reference flow(s).

The FU provides a fair means of comparison between the REVEAL energy storage system and conventional energy storage systems. The function of both products therefore needs to be consistent between both. The function provided by both energy storage systems is to provide heat and electricity in winter during peak demand, and the measure of this function is the amount of energy stored. This leads to the following functional unit:

1 MJ electricity and heat output available in winter from long term stored energy

2.4 System boundaries

The LCA of the REVEAL energy storage system is a cradle-to-grave so all lifecycle stages are considered. This includes the production of aluminium from Al₂O₃, produced from the REVEAL system itself. This carbon free aluminium is then transported to the discharging process where the aluminium will be used to produce energy and heat and the Al₂O₃ and Al(OH)₃ is then returned to produce new carbon free aluminium. **Error!**

Reference source not found. shows a schematic overview of the system boundary of the REVEAL energy system.

FIGURE 2 SYSTEM BOUNDARY DIAGRAM FOR THE ALUMINIUM ENERGY STORAGE SYSTEM. THE DOTTED LINE REPRESENTS THE SYSTEM BOUNDARY, ALUMINIUM IS PRODUCED PARTLY FROM VIRGIN Al_2O_3 AND FROM RECYCLED Al_2O_3 FROM THE REVEAL SYSTEM. THE ALUMINIUM IS USED TO PRODUCE ELECTRICITY AND HEAT IN THE DISCHARGING PROCESS. THE Al_2O_3 PRODUCED IN THIS PROCESS FEEDS BACK INTO THE ALUMINIUM PRODUCTION.

Life cycle stages REVEAL energy storage system:

- **Charging process: Power-to-Alu** – This stage includes the raw materials to produce aluminium, the carbon free anodes and cathodes, the aluminium smelter facility, energy, water use, waste and potential emitted emissions. For this process carbon free aluminium will be produced in Iceland, using carbon free inert anodes and cathodes. The energy needed to produce this aluminium will be taken from the Icelandic grid mix and produced with 100% renewable energy sources.
- **Transport:** This stage includes all transportation of the aluminium from where the aluminium smelter is located to the user (such as households Switzerland) and the return trip of the Al_2O_3 or $Al(OH)_3$ back to the smelter/calcination. The system under study will focus on producing aluminium in Iceland and transporting the aluminium to Switzerland by container ship, train and lorry.
- **Discharging process: Alu-to- H_2** – This stage includes the Alu-to- H_2 converter, the required water input, and the energy needed to produce the H_2 and separate Al_2O_3 or $Al(OH)_3$. The discharging process takes place at residential buildings, where the heat released from the chemical conversion (oxidizing Alu) is recovered and used to meet space heat and domestic hot water demands in winter. The H_2 generated in this process is supplied to the fuel cell system.

- Discharging process: Fuel cell – This stage includes the fuel cell itself and the system (meaning the whole appliance that will be placed at the residential building), and the energy needed to operate the fuel cell. Like the Alu-to-H₂, the fuel cell will also be in residential buildings that will use the electricity and heat in the building.

It is important to align the system boundaries of the alternative technologies with those of the REVEAL energy storage system to ensure a fair and meaningful comparison in the LCA. Consistent system boundaries help avoid misleading conclusions by ensuring that all technologies are assessed on the same basis, including comparable life cycle stages, inputs, and outputs. This alignment is essential for accurately evaluating environmental performance.

Alternative energy storage systems:

As described above in section 2.2, the REVEAL energy storage system will be compared with three alternative systems:

1. Power-to-H₂-to-Energy
 2. Power-to-CH₄/Methanol-to-Energy
 3. Natural gas-to-Energy, using CHP
- Charging process: Power-to-H₂ and power-to-CH₄/methanol – This stage includes the electrolyzer that will split water into H₂ and O₂, the facility, energy, and water use. It also includes additional steps to make H₂ transportable, either by liquefaction (cryogenic) or compression (pressurized form). For the power-to-CH₄/methanol, the extra process steps for methanation/methanol synthesis of the H₂ and CO₂ will be included. These steps account not only for the energy required for synthesis but also for the efforts and energy inputs involved in capturing the necessary CO₂. In the comparison with the fossil alternative of combined heat and power system, this step includes the extraction of natural gas.
 - Transport: This stage includes all transportation of the H₂ from Iceland to households in Switzerland.
 - Discharging process: H₂/CH₄/Methanol/gas-to-Energy – This process includes the fuel cell that converts H₂ into electricity at a household as well as the combustion processes of methanol and CH₄ to produce electricity in the power-to-CH₄/methanol alternative. Included here are the energy to make the conversion, any other raw material intakes, emissions from the conversion and the converters itself. For the combined heat and power system, this step includes the combustion of natural gas.

2.5 Selected cut-off criteria and cut-offs

No cut-off percentage is defined for processes and flows, as the intention is to make the assessment as complete as possible. Processes, inputs, or outputs within the system boundaries will only be excluded from this study if suitable data is not available and their contribution can be clearly argued to be insignificant. Those cases will be reported in the final report as data exclusions.

2.6 Data and data quality requirements

2.6.1 Time boundary for data

Since the REVEAL project develops a new technology to store energy, the time boundary for the data is not very long. The project runs over four years, and the new techniques are tested during the project. Data for the power-to-Alu and Alu-to-power process is measured at lab scale and represents the data at one point in time.

2.6.2 Geographic boundary for data

For this study, the geographical scope will be Iceland and Switzerland. The Power-to-Alu plant will be based in Iceland, which will produce the carbon free aluminium. The aluminium will then be shipped to Switzerland where the Alu-to-Energy plant will produce heat and electricity for Swiss households in winter.

Different geographical scopes to be determined later in the project will be assessed within a scenario analysis. For the Power-to-Alu other countries will be included that have (potentially) a yearly renewable energy supply, whereas for the Alu-to-power process countries with a high energy demand at winter will be assessed.

2.6.3 Data sources

Primary data will be used to produce carbon free aluminium, the Alu-to-Energy converter, shipping distances and fuel cell efficiencies. Most primary data will be measured in lab-scale setups since the project includes a new technology. A scenario analysis will include scale-up assumptions to test the impact when the system is at full scale production.

Secondary data will be used for all remaining processes and the alternative energy storage systems. We intend to use ecoinvent 3.10 for the background data [4] and supplement where needed with data from literature. One important literature source used is the PEF Methodology [5]. The PEF method provides default average values for various life cycle stages. These values are used for stages in the life cycle and not directly influenced by the REVAL project. Further detail on additional literature used will be added later.

2.6.4 Data collection

Primary data will be collected by the consortium partners responsible for the development of the new technology. Data of the power-to-Alu process will be measured by Arctus and IceTec, Ost will provide data for the Alu-to-H₂ conversion, for both the process and the converter. EH-Group will provide data for the H₂-to-Power process, by measuring their fuel cell prototype. Data will be measured from prototypes and lab-scale tests, which also include measured actual efficiencies of the smelter, converter and fuel cell. Due to the novelty of the technology and the small-scale tests, it is expected that there will be a higher level of uncertainty in the collected data. Additionally, some data points may not yet be measured, reducing the completeness of the data. In such cases, assumptions will be made based on expert judgment from the relevant partners.

The data about the alternative scenarios will be gathered using secondary databases like ecoinvent 3.10 [4] and supplemented with scientific papers and other published literature regarding the alternative energy storage scenarios. In case of limited data available, we will do our best to fill the gaps with expert judgment.

This can lead to inconsistencies between the gathered data of the REVEAL energy storage systems and the alternative energy storage systems in terms of data quality (e.g. completeness, uncertainty, and precision); and also with regards to methodological decisions such as system boundaries and allocation principles (see next paragraph 2.7).

2.6.5 Data quality

The partners that are responsible for collecting the data (as mentioned in section 2.6.4) will make sure that the data is of high quality, meaning it is all measured data from lab tests and tests with the developed prototypes. When data cannot be measured, the partners will make assumptions based on expert judgement.

To assure the data quality is sufficient the study will use a semi-quantitative data scoring assessment to curate the data used within this LCA, and to understand where there are possibilities of error or areas for improvement. This semi-quantitative data scoring assessment will be done with the Pedigree Matrix from Weidema and Wesnaes [6] (see **Error! Reference source not found.**). This matrix is also used to quantify data uncertainty in the ecoinvent database, which are used for the background data. The method to change the point estimates to probability distributions is based on this pedigree matrix. Within this matrix, the data quality is evaluated based on the following indicators:

- Reliability
- Completeness
- Temporal correlation
- Geographic correlation
- Technological correlation

The data quality of the most important data points in the models will be assessed by assigning a score between one (best) and five (worst) for each of the indicators. The most important data points will be identified as the data points which have the highest influence on the results, as explained in section **Error! Reference source not found.** Score assignment is done according to the categorization provided in the pedigree matrix by Weidema and Wesnaes [6].

Data quality requirements.

In ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 studies, a data quality score below 3 is considered generally acceptable, although there are no set requirements. In this study, we therefore set the threshold requirement for the quality of the most important data points to be below 3. However, we consider a score of 3 as relatively poor quality, so we will assess critically the data points with threshold.

Uncertainty assessment.

Based on the outcomes of the pedigree matrix, uncertainty distributions with standard deviations for the most relevant processes are defined and used in a Monte Carlo assessment. The Monte Carlo assessment

takes a random value from the uncertainty distribution for each uncertain data input and calculates and stores the LCA results for this set of sampled values. The procedure is repeated 10000 times.

2.7 Allocation procedures

When a process produces multiple outputs (multi-functional), or products find a useful application in a next life cycle at the end-of-life of the current one, then the system boundaries require further investigation. What benefits and burden are attributed (or 'allocated') to which life cycle?

According to ISO 14040/14044, allocation should be handled using the stepwise approach presented below.

- Step 1: Wherever possible, allocation should be avoided.
- Step 2: When unavoidable, the system's inputs and outputs should be allocated among its different products or functions in a manner that reflects their underlying physical relationships.
- Step 3: When a physical relationship cannot be established or used as the basis for allocation, inputs should be allocated between the products and functions based on other relationships, such as economic allocation – based on market value.

2.7.1 Multi-functional processes

We will identify cases of multi-functional processes (i.e. processes which result in multiple outputs, or co-products) within the system boundaries and assess the most appropriate approach for handling them. In the primary data, where allocation can be avoided, the processes will be subdivided. For the remaining cases, allocation will be used to determine what part of the impacts are attributed to the products under study.

We anticipate the following multi-functional process:

- Al-to-H₂ – This process produces heat and H₂. For this process we suggest allocating by unit of energy, treating 1 MJ of heat the same way as 1 MJ of electricity. A sensitivity assessment will be done to allocate by weighted units of energy, weighting electricity higher than heat as it has a thermodynamic (exergetic) higher value.

Any additional multi-output process will be identified during the data collection phase. Subsequently, the appropriate approach will be selected and documented in the final report and subjected to a sensitivity analysis.

2.7.2 End of Life

For the **end-of-life** of lost alumina, we will apply the closed-loop approximation method, as this is the most widely used and accepted approach within the industry. As supported by the broader metal sector, the European aluminium industry strongly recommends assessing the environmental benefits of recycling using the end-of-life recycling approach, rather than the recycled content approach [7].

The recycled content method is considered incomplete and of limited environmental relevance for metal products. In contrast, the end-of-life recycling approach takes a full product life cycle and material stewardship perspective, accounting for the fate of materials after use and their resulting output flows.

For **end-of-life allocation** of other materials like disused smelter or converter components that cannot be recycled, the cut-off approach (0-100) is used as default. This is used in both the background data (ecoinvent cut-off by classification system) and the foreground processes to ensure consistency.

According to the cut-off approach, the environmental impacts from collecting, processing, and storing material for reuse after its initial use are not attributed to the waste product. The underlying philosophy of this approach is that primary (first) production of materials is allocated to the primary user of a material. If a material is recycled, the primary producer does not receive any benefits or burdens for the provision of recyclable materials. For waste that is not recycled, such as materials sent to landfill or incineration, the impacts are assigned to the respective functional unit.

For

2.8 Impact assessment method

The Environmental Footprint (EF) impact categories will be used in the study. The Environmental Footprint impact assessment method documented in the most recent version of the PEF method is used, namely version 3.1. This impact assessment method is assembled by the European Commission as a result of a consensus process based on the state-of-the art science per impact category. This widely accepted method is selected as it provides a wide range of impact categories across which the potential environmental impact can be interpreted. This impact assessment method was selected as it is becoming industry best-practice for stakeholders in Europe and it is recommended by the European Aluminium Association.

Results of all impact categories contained within this method will be reported on; however, a particular focus on analysis and interpretation will be given to those most relevant for the Aluminium sector in general and for the REVEAL system under study, as explained in section 2.9.

The full list of characterization factors is available at the [European Platform on LCA | EPLCA \(europa.eu\)](https://eplca.europa.eu) (Table 1). The sub-categories ‘climate change –fossil’, ‘climate change – biogenic’ and ‘climate change - land use and land use change’, are reported separately if they each show a contribution of more than 5% to the total score of climate change.

A sensitivity analysis will also be conducted using the ReCiPe (H/A) methodology [8] to assess the implications of using a different impact assessment method.

TABLE 1: EF 3.1 IMPACT CATEGORIES

EF impact category	Impact category indicator	Unit	Characterization model
Climate change	Radiative forcing as Global Warming Potential (GWP100)	kg CO ₂ eq	Baseline model of 100 years of the IPCC
Ozone depletion	Ozone Depletion Potential (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq	Steady-state ODPs
Human toxicity, cancer	Comparative Toxic Unit for humans (CTU _h)	CTU _h	USEtox model 2.1
Human toxicity, non-cancer	Comparative Toxic Unit for humans (CTU _h)	CTU _h	USEtox model 2.1
Particulate matter	Impact on human health	disease incidence	PM method recommended by UNEP
Ionising radiation, human health	Human exposure efficiency relative to ²³⁵ U	kBq ²³⁵ U eq	Human health effect model as developed by Dreicer et al. 1995

Photochemical ozone formation, human health	Tropospheric ozone concentration increase	kg NMVOC eq	LOTOS-EUROS model as implemented in ReCiPe 2008
Acidification	Accumulated Exceedance (AE)	mol H ⁺ eq	Accumulated Exceedance
Eutrophication, terrestrial	Accumulated Exceedance (AE)	mol N eq	Accumulated Exceedance
Eutrophication, freshwater	Fraction of nutrients reaching freshwater end compartment (P)	kg P eq	EUTREND model as implemented in ReCiPe
Eutrophication, marine	Fraction of nutrients reaching marine end compartment (N)	kg N eq	EUTREND model as implemented in ReCiPe
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	Comparative Toxic Unit for ecosystems (CTUe)	CTUe	USEtox model 2.1
Land use	- Soil quality index ¹ - Biotic production - Erosion resistance - Mechanical filtration - Groundwater replenishment	- Dimensionless (pt) - kg biotic production - kg soil - m ³ water - m ³ groundwater	Soil quality index based on LANCA
Water use	User deprivation potential (deprivation-weighted water consumption)	m ³ world eq	Available Water Remaining (AWARE) as recommended by UNEP, 2016
Resource use², minerals and metals	Abiotic resource depletion (ADP ultimate reserves)	kg Sb eq	CML 2002

2.9 Identification of most relevant impact categories, life cycle stages and processes

The methodological guidance for the environmental assessment of aluminium [7] recommend including the following impact categories, as they are seen relevant to the aluminum sector in general.

- Climate Change
- Ozone depletion
- Particulate matter
- Ionising radiation, human health
- Photochemical ozone formation, human health
- Acidification
- Eutrophication, Marine
- Eutrophication, Terrestrial
- Eutrophication, Freshwater

¹ This index is the result of the aggregation, performed by JRC, of the 4 indicators provided by LANCA model as indicators for land use.

² The results of this impact category shall be interpreted with caution, because the results of ADP after normalization may be overestimated. The European Commission intends to develop a new method moving from depletion to dissipation model to better quantify the potential for conservation of resources.

As the REVEAL energy storage system adopts a different technology of producing aluminium, this study might overlook relevant impact categories by only focusing on the relevant impact categories recommended by the European aluminium association and therefore this study will also identify the most relevant impact categories and life cycle stages of the REVEAL system, to assist targeted interpretation.

The relevance is determined following the PEF [9] method shown in Table 2. This method involves the following steps: First, the impacts across all impact categories are calculated. Then, normalization and weighting factors from EF 3.1 are applied to determine how each category contributes to the single score. The impact categories are ranked based on their contribution to this single score, from highest to lowest. Finally, the categories that together account for more than 80% of the total score are identified as the most relevant impact categories. Negative values are converted to absolute values and the percentages are recalculated to also account for negative values. The decision to focus on 'most relevant' impact categories based on the 'hotspot' analysis from the PEF [9] methodology aims to highlight key environmental areas for attention. While all impact categories are relevant and reported, this portion of the analysis prioritizes hotspots to enhance the report's practicality.

Therefore, this approach is applied to give direction to where high granular result analysis and interpretation should be targeted. It should be noted that this approach uses weighting in the selection of most relevant impact categories; however, we explicitly do not report on weighted results, nor do we reduce the results to a single overall score or number. Nevertheless, it should be noted that identification of most relevant impact categories is partially based on value-choices in the weighting set.

TABLE 2. OVERVIEW OF METHODOLOGY FOR IDENTIFYING THE MOST RELEVANT IMPACT CATEGORIES (SOURCED FROM TABLE 27 OF THE PEF METHOD,)

Item	At what level does relevance need to be identified?	Threshold
Most relevant impact categories	Normalized and weighted results	Impact categories when ranked from high to low cumulatively contributing at least 80% of the total environmental impact
Most relevant life cycle stages	For each most relevant impact category	All life cycle stages contributing cumulatively more than 80% to that impact category, considering absolute values.
Most relevant processes	For each most relevant life cycle stage	All processes contributing cumulatively more than 80% to that life cycle stage, considering absolute values.

2.10 Assumptions

Any assumptions made in this study will be transparently documented and added to the deliverable of T6.2 and T6.4. The most relevant assumptions will be subjected to sensitivity analysis to assess their influence on the overall conclusions of the study. A key sensitivity analysis which we anticipate being useful is the choice of secondary data for key data points.

Some assumptions we already foresee are:

- The carbon free aluminium will be produced in Iceland and the energy will be used in Switzerland.

- Lab-scale experiments will be extrapolated to full production to calculate the environmental footprint of the REVEAL energy storage system.
- All processes that require energy, e.g. calcination of the $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$, production of virgin alumina etc. will use renewable energy sources.

2.11 Limitations of the study

The limitations of this study will be defined and documented during the execution. Limitations we can identify at this stage are as follows.

- The REVEAL energy storage system is still being developed and tested at the lab-scale. Data is based on lab-scale tests, and assumptions for scaling up need to be made.
- Emission data still needs to be measured at the lab-scale.
- Life Cycle Assessments (LCA) of emerging technologies face significant uncertainties due to the early-stage nature of the systems being evaluated. Key challenges include reliance on lab-scale or pilot-scale results and assumptions made when scaling up to commercial production. Methodological choices—such as system boundaries, allocation methods, and functional units—further influence outcomes, while future market behavior and technological interactions add complexity. Additionally, uncertainties arise from projecting future energy systems or applying generalized data across regions. To manage these uncertainties, sensitivity and scenario analyses will be used to provide a more robust and transparent assessment.

Any further limitations defined in this study will be clearly documented and added to this list in the deliverable of T6.2 and T6.4.

3. References

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Appendix A – Pedigree matrix

The pedigree matrix method used for measuring the quality of data in this study requires that each flow type is attributed to a basic uncertainty factor which is then combined with “additional uncertainty factors” using the following equation to calculate a squared geometric standard deviation:

$$SSD_{g95} = \sqrt{\exp[\ln(U1)^2 + \ln(U2)^2 + \ln(U3)^2 + \ln(U4)^2 + \ln(U5)^2 + \ln(Ub)^2]}$$

With:

- U1: uncertainty factor of reliability
- U2: uncertainty factor of completeness
- U3: uncertainty factor of temporal correlation
- U4: uncertainty factor of geographic correlation
- U5: uncertainty of other technological correlation

The five data quality indicators (DQI) are evaluated by the Pedigree matrix [10] using scores from 1 to 5. Scores have been assigned to the data in the SimaPro model based on the criteria presented in the Pedigree matrix as shown in Table 3.

TABLE 3: PEDIGREE MATRIX SCORES

DQI	Description	Value
Reliability	Unspecified	N/A
	Verified data based on measurements	1
	Verified data based on assumptions or non-verified data based on measurements	2
	Non-verified data partly based on qualified estimates	3
	Qualified estimate (e.g. by industrial expert)	4
	Non-qualified estimate	5
Completeness	Unspecified	N/A
	Representative data from all sites relevant for the market considered, over an adequate period to even out normal fluctuations	1
	Representative data from >50% of the sites relevant for the market considered, over an adequate period to even out normal fluctuations	2
	Representative data from only some sites (<<50%) relevant for the market considered or >50% of sites but from shorter periods	3
	Representative data from only one site relevant for the market considered or some sites but from shorter periods	4
	Representative unknown or data from a small number of sites and from shorter periods	5
Temporal correlation	Unspecified	N/A
	Less than 3 years of difference to the time period of the dataset	1
	Less than 6 years of difference to the time period of the dataset	2
	Less than 10 years of difference to the time period of the dataset	3
	Less than 15 years of difference to the time period of the dataset	4
	Age of data unknown or more than 15 years of difference to the time period of the dataset	5
Geographical correlation	Unspecified	N/A
	Data from area under study	1
	Average data from larger area under study is included	2
	Data from area with similar production conditions	3
	Data from area with slightly similar production conditions	4
	Data from unknown or distinctly different area (North America instead of Middle East, OECD-Europe instead of Russia)	5
Further technological correlation	Unspecified	N/A
	Data from enterprises, processes and materials under study	1
	Data from processes and materials under study (i.e. Identical technology) but from different enterprises	2
	Data from processes and materials under study but from different technology	3
	Data on related processes or materials	4
	Data on related processes on laboratory scale or from different technology	5